

Effectiveness of selected parturients positions on level of pain adaptation during first stage of labour among primigravida mothers admitted in hospitals of selected areas

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Received: Apr 10, 2026

Accepted: Apr 30, 2026

Published: May 04, 2026

ABSTRACT

Background: Maternal care during the different stages of labour should be targeted towards the promotion of maternal, foetal, and neonatal health status. Maternal position is very important in labour and delivery Care. Nevertheless, there is controversial results regarding the effect of maternal position in labour. Maternal position during the labour were the upright and lying positions. The outcome measures included duration of the different stages of labour, persistent posterior position, postpartum haemorrhage, maternal pain, anxiety and fatigue. The results revealed that different maternal positions during the first- and second-stage of labour did not affect maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes. However, all studies stated that low risk mothers should have the chance for choosing a comfortable position in the different stages of labour.

Objectives: A study to assess Effectiveness of selected parturient positions of level of pain adaptation during first stage of labour among primigravida mothers admitted in hospitals of selected areas.

Methods: A quantitative, Quasi-experimental one group pre-test post-test research design was adopted. The study was conducted among 30 Primigravida mothers with first stage of labour selected using non-probability convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured demographic proforma, self prepared pain adaptation scale. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and inferential statistics including Chi-square test were used for comparison and association analysis.

Results: The study findings revealed that the Pre-intervention assessment showed that Deals with analysis of data related to assessment of pain adaptation levels. Before the administration of selected parturient positions, the majority (66.7%) of mothers had Poor pain adaptation (score 7-9), and 16.7% had Very Poor pain adaptation (score 10). Only 16.7% demonstrated Moderate adaptation. No mothers showed Good or Complete adaptation during the pre-test. After the intervention, there was a notable shift. Half of the mothers (50%) exhibited good adaptation (score 1-3), and 33.3% showed Moderate adaptation (score 4-6). Furthermore, 6.7% achieved Complete adaptation. Only 10% remained in the Poor adaptation category, with none in the Very Poor category.

Conclusion: Parturient positions was effective in improving pain adaptation level among primigravida mothers, resulting in better comfortable position and enhanced maternal outcomes.

Keywords: parturient positions, labour, adaptation, intrapartum, postpartum.

INTRODUCTION

Maternal health promotion plans should facilitate the provision, maintenance, and enhancement of their health status. In addition, these plans should address the improvement of the quality of labour care, mitigation of side effects, reduction of maternal and neonatal mortality, and satisfaction of mothers with the provided services. The care plans must be evidence-based and prioritize the prevention and health promotion programs over the expensive diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. Maternal position is one of the obstetric care in the labour wards. Consideration of maternal position in the labour wards is indicative of a supportive environment for delivery leading to an improved sense of competence and personal success in mothers during the intrapartum and postpartum periods.

Maternal position is a remarkable point of maternal care during the labour process, which is neglected in many cases by the care providers of the labour wards. Placement of mothers in a lying position during the course of delivery is one of the common interventions in the current century

Before the 17th century, delivery at the upright position was popular in the Western countries, and the lying position was performed only in cases with an indication of operative delivery. Afterward, the lying position became common due to the comfort of the birth companion. delivery at the upright position is still common in the societies lacking modern medicine. In this regard, reported that out of 76 studied traditional cultures, only 14 cases chose the maternal supine lying position for labour. Consideration of maternal rights obligates the care providers to give the choice of childbirth position to the mothers. The position that mothers choose for delivery depends on several complicated factors and the norms of their society. In societies that labour is carried out in the health centres and hospitals, the social norms are affected by the expectations and requests of the obstetricians.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Maternal care during the different stages of labour should be targeted towards the promotion of maternal, foetal, and neonatal health status. Maternal position is very important in labour and delivery Care. Nevertheless, there is controversial results regarding the effect of maternal position in labour. The present study reviewed the effect of maternal position on maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes. Methods: In this systematic review, databases including PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar as well as Persian databases of Magi ran and SID, were searched and all related articles between 2005 to 2018 were retrieved. The quality of the studies was examined using the Joanna Briggs Institute tool. Results: 17 clinical trials performed on 4,848 subjects were reviewed. Maternal position during the labour were the upright and lying positions. The outcome measures included duration of the different stages of labour, persistent posterior position, postpartum haemorrhage, maternal pain, anxiety and fatigue. The foetal and neonatal outcomes entailed Apgar score, umbilical venous blood pH, need for neonatal resuscitation, and need for hospitalization in NICU. The results revealed that different maternal positions during the first- and second-stage of labour did not affect maternal, foetal, and neonatal outcomes. However, all studies stated that low risk mothers should have the chance for choosing a comfortable position in the different stages of labour.

NEED OF THE STUDY

Non-pharmacological interventions, such as adopting different parturient positions, have been widely advocated to enhance comfort, facilitate labour progression, and reduce the perception of pain. Various positions, including upright, standing, walking, squatting, lateral, and hands-and-knees, influence pelvic biomechanics, fetal descent, and overall labour experience. However, there is a need for more evidence-based studies comparing the effectiveness of different positions in reducing pain perception and promoting adaptation during the first stage of labour.

Childbirth medicalization has reduced the parturients opportunity to labour and deliver in a spontaneous position like upright, lateral constricting her to assume the recumbent one. The aim of the study was to use alternative positions in terms of labour process, type of delivery, neonatal wellbeing, and intrapartum foetal head rotation. This study aimed to given different position and helps in progress of labour and concerning the birth process and outcomes among women who have given birth in primary health care settings.

METHODOLOGY

The present study adopted a quantitative research approach with a Quasi-experimental one group pre-test post-test design to assess the effectiveness of selected parturient positions of level of pain adaptation during first stage of labour among primigravida mothers admitted in hospitals of selected areas.

The study was conducted in selected hospital areas over a period of 28 days. The target population included primigravida mothers with first stage of labour at selected areas. A total sample of 30 primigravida mothers was selected using a non-probability convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a selected demographic variable, Self prepared pain adaptation scale. The tool was validated by experts and reliability was established prior to the study. A pilot study was conducted to assess feasibility. Ethical approval was obtained and informed consent was taken from participants before data collection. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics

RESULT**SECTION I****DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE****TABLE 1 Association Between Post-test Level of Pain Adaptation and Selected Demographic Variables (n=30)**

Sr. No	Demographic Variable	Good (< Median)	Poor (\geq Median)	df	Cal. X ₂ Value	Table X ₂ Value	Significance (p<0.05)
1.	Age	2	2	2	1.15	5.99	Not Significant
2.	Socioeconomic Status	7	3	2	3.45	5.99	Not Significant
3.	Area of Residence	8	4	2	2.12	5.99	Not Significant
4.	Antenatal Visits	1	6	2	9.85*	5.99	Significant
5.	Gestational Age	12	6	1	5.60*	3.84	Significant

Description of samples (Primigravida mother) based on their demographic data in terms of frequency and percentage

Age: The majority of the mothers (73.3%) were in the age group of 21-30 years, while 13.3% were below 20 years, and 13.3% were between 31-40 years.

Socioeconomic Status: Half of the participants (50%) belonged to the lower-middle class, 33.3% were from the middle class, and 16.7% were from a poor socioeconomic background.

Area of Residence: Regarding residence, 40% lived in urban areas, 33.3% in rural areas, and 26.7% in slums.

Antenatal Visits: The data shows that 50% of mothers had four antenatal visits, 26.7% had three, 16.7% had two, and only 6.7% had one visit.

Gestational Age: A majority (60%) had a gestational age of 37 to 38 weeks, while 40% were between 38 to 40 weeks.

Section II

Analysis of Data Related to Effectiveness of Level of Pain Adaptation Among Primigravida Mothers (Pre-test and Post-test). N=30

Level of Pain Adaptation	Score Range	Pre-test (Before Intervention) (f)	Pre-test (Before Intervention) (%)	Post-test (After Intervention) (f)	Post-test (After Intervention) (%)
Complete Adaptation	0	0	0 %	2	6.7 %
Good Adaptation	1-3	0	0 %	15	50.0 %
Moderate Adaptation	4-6	5	16.7 %	10	33.3 %
Poor Adaptation	7-9	20	66.7 %	3	10.0 %
Very Poor Adaptation	10	5	16.7 %	0	0 %
Total		30	100 %	30	100 %

Pre-test: Before the administration of selected parturient positions, the majority (66.7%) of mothers had Poor pain adaptation (score 7-9), and 16.7% had Very Poor pain adaptation (score 10). Only 16.7% demonstrated Moderate adaptation. No mothers showed Good or Complete adaptation during the pre-test.

Post-test: After the intervention, there was a notable shift. Half of the mothers (50%) exhibited good adaptation (score 1-3), and 33.3% showed Moderate adaptation (score 4-6). Furthermore, 6.7% achieved Complete adaptation. Only 10% remained in the Poor adaptation category, with none in the Very Poor category.

Comparison of Effectiveness of Selected Parturient Positions on Level of Pain Adaptation Among Primigravida Mothers (Pre-test vs Post-test) (n=30)

Group	Pre-test Mean	Pre-test SD	Post-test Mean	Post-test SD	Mean Difference	SE	df	Calculated 't' Value	Table 't' Value	Significance (p<0.05)
Experimental Group	8.40	1.58	4.20	1.12	4.20	0.35	29	12.00*	2.05	Significant

The average pain adaptation score in the Pre-test was 8.40 with a Standard Deviation (SD) of 1.58, indicating poor adaptation.

The average score in the Post-test was 4.20 with a Standard Deviation (SD) of 1.12, indicating an improvement to a moderate level of adaptation.

The Mean Difference observed between the pre-test and post-test was 4.20.

The calculated 't' value of 12.00 is greater than the table 't' value of 2.05 at 29 degrees of freedom.

DISCUSSION

The discussion brings the research report to a close by interpreting the major findings of the study in relation to the objectives and previous research. The present study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of selected parturient positions on the level of pain adaptation during the first stage of labour among primigravida mothers. The initial assessment revealed that a majority of the primigravida mothers had poor pain adaptation. In the pre-test, 66.7% of the mothers exhibited poor adaptation and 16.7% showed very poor adaptation, while none of the mothers demonstrated good or complete adaptation. This indicates that most mothers experienced difficulty in coping with labour pain before the intervention. Following the implementation of selected parturient positions, a significant improvement was observed in the post-test. About 50% of the mothers achieved good pain adaptation and 33.3% showed moderate adaptation, while 6.7% reached complete adaptation. Only 10% remained in the poor adaptation category and none were in the very poor category. This clearly shows that the intervention was effective in improving pain adaptation among primigravida mothers. The effectiveness of the intervention was further supported by statistical analysis. The mean pretest score was 8.40, which reduced to 4.20 in the post-test. The calculated 't' value was 12.00 at 29 degrees of freedom, which was much higher than the table value of 2.05 at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the difference between pre-test and post-test scores was statistically significant and the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, selected parturient positions were effective in reducing labour pain and improving pain adaptation.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study lead to the conclusion that the use of selected parturient positions is a highly effective non-pharmacological intervention for improving pain adaptation in primigravida mothers during the first stage of labor. The significant reduction in pain scores and the notable shift toward better adaptation levels post-intervention underscores the clinical utility of these positions. Additionally, the significant role of antenatal visits and gestational age suggests that maternal preparedness and physical maturity are critical factors in labor pain management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researcher expresses sincere and heartfelt gratitude to all those who have contributed to the successful completion of this study. First and foremost, I am deeply indebted to my respected guide for her expert guidance, valuable suggestions, continuous encouragement, and constant support throughout the research work. I extend my sincere thanks to the Principal and all faculty members of the institution for their support, encouragement, and for providing me with the opportunity to conduct this study. I am also grateful to the hospital authorities and nursing staff for granting permission and extending their cooperation during the data collection process. I would like to express my special thanks to all the primigravida mothers who willingly participated in the study. Their cooperation, patience, and trust made this study possible. I am thankful to my classmates and seniors for their constant help, motivation, and moral support during the study period. I also acknowledge all those who directly or indirectly contributed to this work but may not have been mentioned individually.

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